

Policy Paper 3

The Audience Matters. Some (Radical?) Thoughts on Future Perspectives for Public Service Media

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Executive Summary

This policy paper argues that public service media can remain strong and democratically relevant only if they systematically integrate the audience perspective, understood not merely as reach or consumption but as citizens' diverse democratic expectations.

Core Argument

Democratic communication requires two pillars:

1. Normative soundness of information, and
2. Communicative resonance with citizens' democratic orientations.

Only when both converge can trust, public connection, and democratic agency be sustained.

Democratic Diversity and Audience Expectations

Citizens hold different but overlapping understandings of democracy, mainly:

- **Representative democracy**, emphasizing informed voting, institutions, and watchdog journalism.
- **Participatory democracy**, emphasizing direct involvement in democratic processes, networking, and connective action.

Research across EU countries shows that these orientations systematically shape how people use, evaluate, and trust news. When media content aligns with these expectations, trust and engagement rise; when it does not, news avoidance and distrust increase.

Strategic Recommendations

Based on MeDeMAP findings, the paper proposes three strategic directions:

1. **Rethink representation**
 - Link representation with forum and functions through citizen formats, neighborhood reporting, and stronger self-representation—and move beyond traditional social categories toward intersectional, real-life social groups.
2. **Increase social diversity within PSM staff**
 - Strengthen accountability to citizens by reflecting diverse lived experiences in newsrooms.
The success of ORF's *ZiB Instagram* and *ZiB TikTok* illustrates how staff diversity enhances resonance with participatory-oriented audiences.

3. Integrate citizen expertise into governance and production

- Involve citizens informally in reviewing routines, formally in co-creation, and institutionally in decision-making structures to rebuild trust and relevance.

Conclusion

Journalism that is normatively excellent but democratically unconnectable risks irrelevance. Making **democratic diversity a guiding principle** for programming, governance, and identity is presented as a key condition for **democratic resilience and the long-term sustainability of public service media**.

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1. Why is it crucial today for public service media to systematically consider the expectations and perceptions of people?

It is a simple but uncomfortable thought: Even the best journalism in the world is democratically irrelevant if it does not reach, resonate with, or increase citizens' agency.

For decades, research and media practice have focused primarily on the supply side of information – content quality, professional standards, normative criteria. All of this is indispensable. But it is not sufficient. As Jesper Strömbäck and colleagues observed (2020, p. 1): “Even a perfectly informative news media environment is of little democratic use if citizens by and large do not consume the news or if they do not trust the news.” And yet, despite how obvious this sounds, the audience perspective is still not systematically embedded as a guiding principle—beyond reach metrics.

However, the crisis of public communication (Davis, 2023) is not only a crisis of quality, it is also a crisis of misalignment: Only when

- normative soundness of information content *and*
- democratic connectability converge,

public service media (PSM) can sustain trust, public connection, and democratic relevance. Public connection depends on communicative resonance with citizens' democratic orientations: today, this resonance must account for another factor long underestimated: democratic diversity. Evidently, citizens have different but overlapping understandings of democracy, which in principle, correspond to two fundamental orientations (Held 2006): representative democracy, which is based on the principles of elected bodies and institutions representing the interests of the citizenry and protecting their rights, and participatory democracy, which aims at the direct inclusion of citizens in the processes of will-formation and decision-making by taking part in the “common work” of keeping an eye on issues affecting themselves, their communities and society as a whole.

Across the European Union, a participatory understanding of democracy is gaining ground. There are some indications of this in the most recent *European Value Survey (EVS/WVS 2024)* based on forms of “non-institutionalized participation”, a concept famously developed by Max Kaase and Samuel H. Barnes in their seminal 1979 work on *Political Action: Mass Participation in Five Western Democracies*. It refers to forms of political action that occur outside the established, conventional channels of a representative democracy and can be considered one of the components of participatory democracy (Bengtsson and Christensen, 2016). On average, around 21% of respondents in 20 EU member states have participated in actions such as petitions, demonstrations, and boycotts, and a further 34% are willing to do so; combined, the potential for active citizen participation is therefore quite high: this is not a fringe phenomenon—it is diversity at the centre of society.

Each understanding of democracy is associated with different expectations regarding the information media: “baseline norms for assessing media and communication vary considerably” across the various notions of democracy (Davis, 2019, p. 19). Qualitative research in the Horizon Europe project *Mapping Media for Future Democracies* confirms quantitative analysis for all and individual EU Member States (Beaufort 2020a, b; 2025; 2026; Beaufort and Seethaler 2021; Seethaler et al. 2026; Beaufort et al. 2025): these expectations systematically shape how people use, evaluate and trust the news. People expect an information environment that matches their individual democratic orientation—consciously or unconsciously—and adjust their information use accordingly. With this, democratic diversity is among the most crucial factors determining whether public communication becomes connectable, alongside platform logics and attention dynamics.

In turn: unmet expectations translate into news avoidance and declining trust. Global news avoidance stands at around 40 percent and is recognized as serious threat to epistemic integrity, communicative equality, and democratic agency. The *Digital News Report (2025)* identifies key reasons, which are: negative emotional impact (approx. 40%), overload (approx. 30%), excessive focus on institutional politics (approx. 30%), lack of connectability (approx. 20%), irrelevance (approx. 20%), and difficulty (approx. 10%). Most of these reasons relate to underlying democratic expectations.

For example, for Austria, it has been shown that only representative-oriented users find sufficient information to meet their needs. On the other hand, the news avoiders group includes a large share of participatory-oriented users whose expectations are insufficiently addressed in the actual information supply. This suggests that news avoiders are not necessarily disengaged from societal affairs—at least not initially. Rather, they encounter an information supply that

does not correspond to their specific needs as democratic citizens. In other words, news avoidance may reflect democratic diversity itself rather than societal apathy.

Democratic functionality of information rests on two pillars: normative soundness and communicative resonance with individual democratic orientation. It is not either-or—it is both: When both come together—when journalism meets democratic diversity in a connectable way—then public connection, trust, and democratic agency become possible. The audience perspective matters.

2. What expectations do people actually have towards the media?

This is the key question. Because it indicates a potential avenue for targeted intervention. The short answer is: It depends. On what?

On the democratic cultures prevailing in a country, and on the democratic orientations of the people.

Different concepts of democracy shape the roles attributed to news media and democratic practices. They shape what citizens expect information to do. And they shape how they use it.

In liberal-representative dynamics, media are expected to support collective action by enabling the “informed citizen.” The central idea here is that citizens make rational choices in the voting booth. They must be informed about relevant societal issues debated in the marketplace of ideas. In this model, citizens primarily assume a more passive role, while the media acts as monitor, disseminator, watchdog, and forum—ideally, presenting plural perspectives, ensuring transparency, scrutinizing power, and delivering fact-based, impartial information of general relevance.

Participatory dynamics are different. Political participation is understood as voluntary work on problem-solving. The focus shifts from supporting the performance of democratic institutions to fostering democracy itself. This is also referred to as “logic of connective action” (Bennett & Segerberg, 2013). Citizens connect their concerns through issue-specific, loosely organized networks. The aim is the “empowered” citizen, and the inclusion (especially) of the so-called silent majority in public debate. In this framework, the media is access provider, connector, and mobilizer. Through exercising representational and participatory functions, media integrate diverse voices, enable bottom-up cooperation, and create spaces where citizens can articulate and contextualize their concerns. Content must be connectable, inclusive, and responsive to diversity.

As mentioned above, research shows that citizens' expectations regarding the democratic function and the quality of information supply closely align with the different democratic roles of the media. For example,

- liberal-representative-oriented users expect macro-level relevance, professional style, and strong monitoring functions;
- participatory-minded users expect content that enables autonomous orientation, inclusion, networking, and meaningful resonance with personal concerns on the micro-level.

To both groups apply that,

- when expectations are met, trust in the media and democratic agency increases;
- otherwise, trust in the media and democratic agency declines.

If people do not find sufficient information offers aligned with their needs, they are likely to lose interest, which can foster news avoidance, declining trust, and, ultimately, structural inequalities.

3. Against this background, how can a resilient democratic citizenry be fostered via information supply?

Scholarly literature that addresses the repositioning of PSM in light of radical changes in media offerings and use and increased competition with global platforms, usually builds on its strengths of high-quality information and independent control, which were developed to support representative democracy. The threat posed by misinformation and disinformation thus often serves as the starting point for reform recommendations. Three approaches therefore dominate the discussion: dedicated fact-checking, enhancing media literacy, and developing genuine PSM online platforms (Sehl 2024). Media literacy initiatives are widely supported and implemented among EBU members, and there are also some fact-checking initiatives, while the implementation of genuine PSM platforms is contested and rather uncertain. However, the first two approaches in particular, as important as they are, arose from a purely defensive position: protecting democratic society against fake news and disinformation. We propose changing perspective and taking *democracy as it is lived in all its diversity* as a starting point for strengthening the legitimacy and relevance of public service media.

Diversity is the key.

“Diversity has become part of the PSM DNA.” One can only emphasise this statement on the EBU website.¹ So far, public service mandates have usually focused on regional diversity and/or the appropriate representation of social groups, reflecting PSM's commitment to universality. In more recent times, for example, gender mainstreaming plans and step-by-step plans to improve access to PSM programmes for people with disabilities have become widespread instruments. These are important steps of inclusion (which, in times of increasing social diversification, is perhaps a better term than ‘universality’). However, as a recent study by Marta Rodríguez-Castro and Azahara Caedo, published by the Austrian public service broadcaster ORF, summarizes, “diversity and inclusion, socio-economic diversity remains an

¹ <https://www.ebu.ch/research/membersonly/report/public-service-media-diversity-strategies> (retrieved on February 19, 2026).

underexplored (although emerging) dimension within the strategic frameworks of most European PSM.” Referring to best-practice examples from the BBC and ARD, the authors advocate “strengthening the connection with citizens and adopting a pluralistic vision of society” (Rodríguez-Castro and Caedo 2025, p. 32). To bring this vision to life, it is not enough to simply produce content targeted at various segments of the population; it requires incorporating the needs of underserved audiences into programme planning and internal governance. Particularly in the information sector, at the very top of people’s needs are the specific needs as democratic citizens. It’s about the question: what are the implications of democratic diversity in society itself for programming mandate, corporate identity, and management structures of public service media.

What is needed going forward?

Based on the results of Horizon Europe project *Mapping Media for Future Democracies*, we recommend considering the following proposals.

(1) Rethinking the PSM’s representational role in light of two kinds of intersection

- first, beyond representations of more traditional societal groups like minorities and women towards representing real-life social groups that result from different combinations of social categories such as class, ethnicity, gender, age, educational level, and many more: addressing and incorporating their notions of democracy could support public connection across diverse groups and promote social cohesion, also and especially by revealing differences and enabling democratic struggle (Carpentier and Wimmer 2025).
- second, through relating the representational role to the forum and participatory role: the former combination would allow for more open arenas that enable networking and interaction such as ‘citizen formats’ and ‘neighbourhood reporting’, the latter for strengthening the importance of self-representation: even in programmes generally conveyed by media professionals, equal power balance between lay participants and professionals can be achieved, promoting mutual understanding and trust (Seethaler et al. 2025; 2026).

(2) Establishing social diversity within PSM staff

Freedom of expression is closely linked to the diversity of viewpoints and voices in the media and the integrity of newsrooms, i.e., the autonomy and accountability of editorial offices (Seethaler et al. 2026). Contrary to the traditional form of accountability as institutionalised democratic control, this is about accountability to citizens and civil society, which has been pursued in EU governance since the 1990s and in EU media policy since the 2010s (Seethaler and Beaufort 2024). The establishment of broader accountability frameworks also includes, as Rodríguez-Castro and Caedo (2025) have pointed out, social diversity *within* PSM staff, thus connecting media professionals and the lived experiences of various communities.

This can be illustrated by a best-practice example from Austria: With *ZiB Instagram* and *ZiB TikTok*, ORF has achieved remarkable reach and resonance among younger and more diverse audiences. The success of both social media formats of ORF's main news brand (which are not shortened versions of the television broadcasts!) cannot be explained simply by platform or by pure attention-span logic. In contrast, they are editorially designed to resonate particularly well with participatory-oriented younger publics, *whose daily lived realities are even reflected in the diversity of the presenters*.

(3) Integrating citizen expertise in programme planning and management

Audience research across Europe and following various methods has shown that supporting and ensuring transparency and accountability as well as inclusive participation in the media are crucial to rebuilding trust (Miconi et al. 2025; Sedlacek and Peissl 2026). The establishment of broader accountability frameworks not only includes social diversity within PSM staff but also participation of citizens in production and management: this can be achieved in several ways:

- In a more informal approach, citizens should be actively involved in rethinking routine practices to detect potential unconscious biases in journalists' perceptions of the democratic needs of audiences and in developing new strategies.
- The next step could be the establishment of working groups of journalists and citizens to develop media products that reflect those needs.
- The most formal approach requires broader involvement of civil society representatives in internal bodies and decision-making processes.

No strategy can be considered a universal remedy, and PSM organisations differ across the European Union—including in terms of attempts by political actors to influence management and reporting (Klimkiewicz et al. 2026): Journalism that is normatively excellent but democratically unconnectable to growing parts of the population risks irrelevance. However, once democratic diversity works as an overarching programmatic PSM orientation, democratic resilience can be sustainable—and thus foster the future sustainability of public service media.

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